

Experimental and analytical evaluation of fiber-matrix interface adhesion

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ABSTRACT

New fibers and matrix materials are being developed constantly to meet the demands of new applications, rapid molding and curing processes and cost reduction targets. New interface improvements, through surface treatments and sizing materials, are also constantly developed to improve adhesion between fiber and matrix (and ultimately the composite properties). Consequently, there is a need to understand the fiber-matrix interface adhesion better so that an optimum choice of the combination can be made.

This paper discusses an effective and efficient test procedure to measure the force required to pull fiber from matrix. The experiment involves pulling 24K, 50K carbon fiber tows bonded with the matrix only in the mid overlap region, thus ensuring that the load is carried only through the fiber-matrix interface. The test results are used to determine fiber-matrix adhesion peak traction separation and the mode II fracture toughness G_{IIc} as required in micromechanics FEA models, where the fiber-matrix interface is represented by cohesive zone elements. This approach clearly distinguishes the effects of surface treatment and sizing on the unidirectional properties. The study also shows the effects of non-circular cross sections of some commercial grade carbon fibers on the fiber-matrix adhesion. This paper presents the results of 3 commercial carbon fibers (each with their proprietary surface treatments) with a rapid curing epoxy matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

The evaluation of new fibers and matrix materials is a continuous process as new materials are introduced to meet application and manufacturing requirements. In composites it has long been established that the fiber and matrix interface plays an important role in the overall material behavior [1-4]. A great deal of effort has been spent on developing mathematical models that include the interface effects [5-8]. A number of test methods are also being proposed and used to measure the interfacial properties [9-12]. It is also been concluded that the test procedures available currently - (single fiber pull, single fiber push) are very difficult to perform specifically for carbon fibers as these filaments are very thin [13-14].

Faced with the challenge of evaluating and selecting a candidate carbon fiber from 3 different suppliers with different manufacturing, sizing and surface treatment processes, it was necessary to establish differences in their composite properties. The 3 candidate fibers have very little difference in their strength and modulus properties. Any rule of mixtures or fiber-matrix micromechanics analysis will result in almost identical unidirectional properties. But the actual composite properties are not always proportional to the fiber strength or modulus.

In micromechanics predictions of the composites properties the strength predictions will not correlate with actual test results unless interfacial adhesion is considered. In earlier micromechanics simulations, attempts were made using the stress criteria to predict crack initiation and element erosion to represent the crack propagation and thus define the fracture behavior of debonding [8].

A simple and effective test method has been developed to determine the fiber matrix interface fracture properties. Cohesive zone elements are subsequently used to represent the fiber matrix interface in a series of micromechanics models.

2 TEST METHOD

In order to evaluate the interface adhesion properties, namely- peak traction force and mode II fracture toughness (G_{2c}), an experimental method was developed in which- spooled fiber tow are used instead of single fiber. This involves the assumption that averaged values can be obtained, which are still sensitive to the fiber shape, size, sizing and surface treatment effects. Figure 1. Shows the schematic of the test specimen.

Figure 1: Schematic of test specimen

Figure 2: Load transfer and overlap length

The load is transferred from fiber to interface to matrix (Figure 2). There is little or no possibility of fiber failure as the pull loads are far less than the fiber break. There is some possibility of crack initiating in the matrix. However, the interface experiences an order of magnitude higher shear stress concentration at the edge of the overlap where the fibers end. This ensures that the crack initiation will be in the interface. The crack growth will be in mode II. The measured values will be that of the interface.

3 SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The fibers in a tow are spread thin, up to 4'' wide (Figure 3), in some cases with a sharp edge. Fibers were separated as much as possible, and curled fibers were straightened. The spread layers of fibers were then overlapped and rolled up avoiding twisting. After a few trials it was possible to ensure good mix of left and right side fibers in the overlap with straight fibers.

Figure 3: Specimen preparation

The main difficulty was controlling the matrix material to be contained within the overlap area. The epoxy system has low viscosity at the time of curing, and will thus flow through the length of the fibers in a capillary action. Various attempts to control the flow, including wax coating of the non-overlap area, failed when the candidate epoxy was very exothermic. The sample preparation was successful only after a measured amount of epoxy (typically just a couple of drops) was applied at the center and allowed to flow by itself and wet the fibers in the overlap area.

Once the resin cured in the overlap section, 20mm x 20mm (glass epoxy composite), tabs were adhered with Loctite 431 instant adhesive, illustrated in Figure 4. The tabs were necessary because preliminary tests conducted without tabs resulted in shear failures at the grips.

Figure 4: Image of tabbed test sample.

4 FIBER PULL OUT TEST RESULTS

Fiber-resin adhesion strength was measured on a 5982 Instron testing system with a 1 kN load cell. Testing was performed at a pull rate of 0.25 mm/s, and pneumatic, serrated grips were used to clamp the tabbed area of the sample. Figure 5 shows typical sample after fiber pull out test.

The typical load-extension curves were linear with abrupt drops in load. A trend was observed when calculating the max load divided by the width of the visible, failed interface. Figure 6 illustrate the load per interface width against extension.

Figure 5: Fiber pull after the Test. The two ends were pulled apart.

Figure 6: Typical load per width vs extension curve of fiber-resin pull out test.

The 3 tested fibers A, B, and C had average pull-out load per interface width values of 172 N/mm, 197 N/mm, and 221 N/mm, respectively.

4.1 Comparison of Transverse and Shear Composite Properties to Pull-Out Results

Table 1 shows the mechanical properties performed on 50% fiber volume test panels prepared by high-pressure resin transfer process. Figure 7 confirms accurate fiber-resin adhesion rankings of the 3 tested fibers.

Mechanical Property	Test Orientation	ASTM Test Method
Flex Strength	[90] _n	D 790
Tensile Strength	[90] _n	D 3039
Iosipescu Strength	[0/90] _n	D 5379
Interlaminar Short Beam Shear	[0/90] _n	D 2344

Table 1: Mechanical properties used to confirm fiber-resin pull-out load results.

Figure 7: Mechanical properties used to confirm fiber-resin pull-out load results.

Based on previous works, transverse properties of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy showed strong relationship to fiber-resin adhesion [1-3]. It has been noted that iosipescu and short beam shear properties are affected by fiber-resin adhesion and friction [1,4]. Figure 7 also shows no correlation between fiber tensile strength to pull-out load.

The fiber pull-out shows a similar trend as with transverse tensile and flexural properties with respect to fiber size. (Figure 8.)

Figure 8: Normalized fiber-resin pull-out load to fiber A vs fiber perimeter.

4.2 Scanning Electron Microscope Fractography and Fiber Dimension Measurement

Fractured tensile samples tested by ASTM D 3039 were sputtered with platinum and observed with a Hitachi S-3700 scanning electron microscope (SEM). In Figure 9, these images were qualitatively ranked for fiber-resin adhesion based on pull-out holes and residual resin on fibers.

Figure 9: SEM images at x1.0k magnification of fractured longitudinal $[0]_n$ tensile samples.

Fiber dimensions were measured through both SEM and optical microscopy. Manual measurements and software analysis determined fiber diameter, perimeter, and area.

5 MICROMECHANICS DISCUSSION – REPEATING CELL

There was significant difference in the size and cross sectional shape of the candidate carbon fibers (Figure 4). It is possible to identify the repeating cells for micromechanics analysis.

Figure 10: Micrograph images of unidirectional carbon composites with 3 different fibers showing filament size and variations. Two of the candidate fibers had kidney shaped cross sections

A simple approach to account for the variations of fiber density and resin rich regions is to use a larger cross section that includes several fibers. But this approach will result in millions of element models that require super computers to run.

Instead it was decided to identify repeating cells of same fiber volume content in a cross section and perform analysis on 4 or 5 different V_f models. A statistical weighted average is used to establish the UD properties. A rigorous test of this approach is being made along with automated pattern recognition tool that identifies the different V_f cells and their distribution from the micrograph scans. A simple weighted average is used to include the distribution as shown in Table 2. A similar approach is presented in [15]

	Fiber Volume Fraction	Longitudinal Strength(MPa)	Distribution	Weighted
Pattern 1	20%	989.0	20%	197
Pattern 2	50%	2418.0	70%	1692
Pattern 3	78%	3778.0	10%	377

Weighted Average **2166**

Table 2: Fiber Volume Fraction Distribution Variation accounted

Unlike in the micromechanics models used for the prediction of the unidirectional composite properties, where the interest is stress and strain and the actual size of the fiber does not matter, in the present analysis of interfacial de-adhesion modeling the micromechanics models dimensions have to be considered.

Figure 11: The base Square and Hexagonal distribution of fiber

Figure 12: Various fiber volume content models

SINGLE

BACK TO BACK

STAGGERED

FACE TO FACE KIDNEY SHAPED FIBERS

Figure 13: Micromechanics Models of Kidney Shaped Fibers

MODEL FOR THE TRANSVERSE SHEAR

HEXA MODEL USED FOR FIBER PULL

Figure 14: Micromechanics for simulation of shear and the fiber pull test

6 COHESIVE ZONE MODELING IN LS-DYNA

The adhesion between fiber and matrix can be effectively represented by cohesive elements that are capable of separating nodes based on the critical fracture energy release rates in a mode I or mode II or even in mixed mode. It is also possible to define linear to complex separation law following the crack initiation.

LS-DYNA was used in the present analysis. Following are the different separation law that can be represented.

Figure 15: Choice of separation laws that can be represented in LS-DYNA

The interface adhesion in the case of fiber pull is in shear mode II. From the initial tests separation is seems to be bi-linear.

Figure 16: Fiber Pull Test simulation, Z stresses in the cohesive elements showing the initiation of de-adhesion.

Figure 17: Effective and shear stress distribution in the matrix.

Figure 18: Pull force and displacement in a single fiber

Figure 17 shows the effective stress in the matrix at the time of initiation of de-adhesion. Figure 18 shows the predicted fiber-pull force displacement in the case of applied force.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The unidirectional properties of carbon composites depend on the fiber surface treatment and sizing and are not necessarily proportional to the fiber strength and modulus. A new fiber pull test procedure has been presented that measures the interfacial failure properties, viz. Peak traction separation force, mode II fracture critical energy release rate G_{IIc} . The test procedure is far simpler than the single fiber pull out test as it provides average interfacial strengths. However further studies are necessary to establish the specimen geometry and preparation process for different fibers and resin systems. Micromechanics models with the cohesive element elements representing fiber matrix interface are used to demonstrate incorporation of tested interfacial properties to predict fiber matrix de-bond failure modes. The combined experimental and analytical effort is very effective in evaluating and selecting carbon fibers.

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